

Modelling and Optimization of High Efficient MPPT Charge Controller for Solar PV Applications

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Abstract : This paper proposes a new method of a high efficient charge controller used for solar PV power generation. The system explains mainly of charge controller connected to a PV and an inverter. The Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) algorithm in the charge controller uses Estimate Perturb and Perturb (EPP) method which gives an estimate for every two perturb process in search of maximum output from the PV panel. A 10W prototyping PV system was executed with a boost DC-DC converter using a Micro controller to execute the proposed MPPT algorithm. Several MPPT algorithms were tested for fast changing environmental conditions, and the test results are examined and compared. It is validated that the EPP method is a promising MPPT control scheme for PV systems. This method notably improves the tracking accuracy and speed of MPPT control mechanism.

Keywords : Charge Controller, EPP method, MPPT, Microcontroller, PV systems

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